

Beyond the Buzzword: A Meta-Review Quantifying Coaching's Impact on Professional Performance, Goal Attainment, and Emotional Competence

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Abstract

Background: In the context of rapid societal changes and increasing demands for professional competence, coaching has emerged as a recognised method for improving employee productivity, motivation, and personal development across industries.

Objective: This study aimed to summarise existing scientific evidence on the effectiveness of coaching interventions in various professional fields and to identify key factors influencing their outcomes.

Methodology: The research design followed a systematic and transparent protocol consistent with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines, ensuring methodological rigour and replicability. The meta-review encompassed empirical studies published between 2016 and 2025 that examined the effectiveness of coaching interventions across professional domains, particularly in business management and healthcare systems. Comprehensive database searches were conducted in Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, PsycINFO, and Google Scholar, yielding 54 studies that met the inclusion criteria. Of these, only 11 randomised controlled trials (RCTs) provided complete statistical indicators necessary for the computation of the effect size (Hedges' g), representing a combined participant pool of 15,278 individuals. The mean effect size and heterogeneity were subsequently calculated in relation to the duration, format, and methodological characteristics of the coaching interventions to identify key determinants of their overall efficacy.

Results: The meta-analysis indicated a significant positive impact of coaching on professional performance, emotional competence, self-awareness, and goal attainment, with a moderate overall effect size (Hedges' $g \approx 0.58$). Higher effectiveness was observed in long-term programmes, individual coaching formats, cognitive-behavioural approaches, externally assessed outcomes, and in the fields of digital transformation management and healthcare.

Conclusion: Coaching interventions significantly and positively influence professional outcomes, with the highest benefits in individualised, long-term applications within management and healthcare.

Unique Contribution: This study integrates large-scale empirical evidence to clarify which structural and methodological factors enhance coaching effectiveness, offering practical insights for program design in diverse professional sectors.

Key Recommendation: Future research should focus on the interaction between coaching duration, delivery format, and assessment method, as well as on sector-specific customisation to optimise program effectiveness.

Keywords: coaching, leadership development, coaching effectiveness, motivation, success, professional self-realisation

Introduction

In today's world of rapid change, high competition, and continuous personal development, motivation and a person's desire for self-realisation play an important role. People and organisations are increasingly seeking effective tools to achieve high results, develop leadership potential, and enhance personal and professional satisfaction. Coaching as a method of professional support and staff development has become widespread in various fields of activity - from corporate governance to healthcare and education. Given the growing need to enhance employee performance, adapt to change, and develop professional skills, coaching interventions are being increasingly integrated into training, development, and management systems (Wang et al., 2022). Coaching is viewed as an individualised process that fosters self-reflection, self-determination, goal setting, motivation, decision-making, and personal growth and self-actualisation, even in the most challenging circumstances (Cannon-Bowers et al., 2023; King et al., 2023).

Over the past decade, the number of studies analysing the effectiveness of coaching has been growing. In particular, meta-analyses have shown a positive impact of coaching programs on various indicators, including increased self-esteem, leadership skills, and performance (de Haan & Nilsson, 2023), as well as psychological well-being (Nicolau et al., 2023).

At the same time, there is a high level of heterogeneity in the results, which necessitates an examination of the primary factors that affect effectiveness. These factors include the duration of coaching, the format of interaction (individual or group), the style of feedback, the source of assessment of the result (self-assessment or external assessment), the type of coaching approach (cognitive-behavioral, positive psychology, integrative), and the professional field in which the person works (Wang et al., 2022; Atad & Grant, 2021).

The article examines the primary scientific evidence of the effectiveness of coaching in various professional fields based on a meta-analysis of research results published from 2016 to 2025. It examines the impact of various coaching approaches, program duration, interaction formats, and other factors that influence the outcome of coaching interventions.

Literature Review

Coaching as a form of professional support is interdisciplinary in nature and is used to develop staff, increase their productivity, build leadership skills and adapt to organisational change (Cannon-Bowers et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). Coaching in the modern sense is a structured process of individual or group work aimed at developing personal potential, setting and achieving goals, shaping adaptive behaviour, and improving well-being (Plotkina & Ramalu, 2024).

It is the right choice of development direction and identification of available opportunities that are key success factors that can contribute to the use of available resources for the development of personal and professional skills and increase the level of self-realisation. In addition, Chen et al. (2024) note that self-development contributes to successful professional development and self-realisation of the individual. Thanks to professional self-realisation, a person strives for self-improvement, the development of his or her moral qualities and the search for a higher meaning of life.

Nowadays, professional self-realisation is considered a process of fully disclosing an individual's professional potential, enabling them to achieve goals and find meaning in life. According to Lahutina et al. (2024), in times of challenges, uncertainty and change, self-realisation is no longer just a desire for self-actualisation, but helps in the search for meaning, preserving one's own identity in the face of stressful factors. In such a period, resilience (psychological stability), the ability to adapt, maintaining a positive emotional state, social integration, and a sense of meaning in life are of great importance (Chen et al., 2024). It is here that self-realisation acts as an integrative factor that combines these aspects and affects the standard of living (Kandiuk-Lebid et al., 2024).

Recent studies have demonstrated a consistent positive impact of coaching on cognitive, emotional, and behavioural outcomes in various professional contexts (Wang et al., 2022; Nicolau et al., 2023). Particular attention is paid in modern scientific literature to the effectiveness of coaching interventions. According to a review by Cannon-Bowers et al. (2023), the effects of coaching vary considerably depending on the type of intervention (individual or group), format (online or offline), program duration, source of feedback, and scope. For example, coaching in the corporate environment has been shown to have a higher productivity effect (Peláez Zuberbuhler et al., 2020; Makedon et al., 2025a; Betto & Garengo, 2023), and in the healthcare sector, it has been found to increase leadership competencies and teamwork (Jones et al., 2016).

Post-pandemic studies that consider the impact of digital technologies on coaching practices are also of interest. In their work, Plotkina and Ramalu (2024) found that the use of online coaching in combination with flexible support tools enhances the effectiveness of programs by improving their adaptability to client needs. At the same time, they emphasise the importance of organisational support and motivational readiness of service recipients. In addition, current research emphasises the importance of professional coaching training (Betto & Garengo, 2023; de Haan & Nilsson, 2023). Thus, the literature review reveals a substantial body of evidence on the effectiveness of coaching in various professional areas, while confirming the high heterogeneity of the results, which makes further meta-analytic research relevant, particularly in considering the

variables and professional context of interventions. The study aims to summarise the available scientific data on the effectiveness of coaching programs in various fields of activity, with further identification of factors that influence the effectiveness of coaching interventions.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a quantitative meta-analysis format to combine empirical evidence on the effectiveness of coaching across various professional areas. The research methodology is based on the recommendations of PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) and modern practices of conducting meta-analyses (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Effect size (Hedges' g)
Source: author's own development

A total of 429 randomized controlled trials were selected for inclusion, and after analysis, out of the 54 studies that met the general inclusion criteria (quantitative assessment of coaching effectiveness, professional context, published within 2016–2025), only 11 provided complete statistical data required for effect size calculation (Hedges' g , 95% CI, and I^2) which included a total sample of 15,278 participants. The remaining studies, although meeting the inclusion criteria for qualitative review, lacked sufficient statistical indicators (e.g., missing standard deviations, incomplete reporting of effect sizes, or non-randomised designs that did not allow for the extraction of comparable metrics).

At the initial stage of the study, the authors conducted a literature search in Scopus, PubMed, Web of Science, PsycINFO, and Google Scholar. Key search terms: coaching effectiveness, meta-analysis of coaching outcomes, executive coaching, behavioural outcomes coaching, leadership coaching meta-review, RCT coaching intervention.

At the second stage, each source was analysed, and the most informative ones were selected, presenting empirical data with Hedges' g performance indicators. After that, the average level of coaching effectiveness was calculated based on the type and duration of interventions, the professional sphere, and the method of evaluating the results, and the conclusions of the work were formulated.

Inclusion criteria. Studies were included in the analysis if they were empirical, meta-analyses, or systematic reviews that contained statistical data on the calculation of the Hedges' g effect size, confidence intervals (95% CI), and heterogeneity index (I^2); had several included studies of at least 10 ($k = 10$); investigated the effectiveness of coaching in a professional context (business, healthcare, education, public administration); and used randomized or experimental designs.

Exclusion criteria: theoretical or review articles without statistical synthesis, as well as studies in which coaching was implemented by a non-specialist (e.g., a manager); duplicate publications, case reports, or qualitative studies without effect measurement.

Statistical analysis. The meta-analysis was conducted using a random effects model. To calculate the mean effect sizes, the authors used data (Hedges' g), taking into account confidence intervals (95% CI). Heterogeneity analysis (I^2 , Cochran's Q) and meta-regression analysis were performed.

Limitations of the study. Despite the results, this study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, there is a high level of heterogeneity in the effects ($I^2 > 70\%$ in most of the included publications), indicating variability in methodology, sample, intervention duration, and types of coaching.

Secondly, a significant number of studies relied on participants' self-assessments, which increases the risk of subjective bias, especially in the context of evaluating the effectiveness of coaching in emotionally sensitive areas. The limited use of external objective indicators makes it difficult to

verify the results. Another limitation is the uneven distribution of professional fields, with most analyses focusing on leaders, technical, pedagogical, and medical fields, while public administration or creative industries remain less studied.

In addition, it should be noted that not all studies have a complete methodology or detailed statistical data (e.g., standard deviations, confidence intervals), which limits the accuracy of secondary analysis. There is also the possibility of publication bias, with studies with positive results being published while insignificant or negative effects remain unpublished. A large proportion of the included studies were conducted in high-income countries (USA, UK, Netherlands), which limits the generalizability of the results to other socio-cultural contexts, including countries with low economies or specific cultures. Another limitation is potential publication bias. Studies with positive results are more likely to be published, while neutral or negative findings may remain unpublished. This could have inflated the pooled effect size. Another limitation is the incomplete reporting of statistical indicators in some primary studies. For instance, several trials did not provide k or I^2 values, which limited the comparability and reduced the comprehensiveness of the pooled analysis.

Results

First, the effectiveness of coaching was investigated, and the effect (Hedges' g) was determined. A Forest plot was created to visualise individual effects and confidence intervals. This allowed to visually assess the consistency of the effects, the direction of influence, and the presence of potential outliers. Fig. 2 illustrates the individual effect sizes (Hedges' g) along with 95% confidence intervals for each empirical study included in the meta-analysis. All studies demonstrate positive Hedges' g values, indicating that coaching interventions are effective in professional performance. The effect sizes range from 0.47 to 0.66, which corresponds to an average level of effectiveness.

Figure 2. Effect size (Hedges' g)
Source: author's own development

The data presented in Table 1 indicate the stable effectiveness of coaching interventions, with most authors demonstrating a medium or moderately high level of effect (from $g = 0.55$ to $g = 0.70$), which indicates a significant impact of coaching on professional performance.

Table 1. Overall effectiveness of coaching interventions, according to the results for each included study

Author(s), year	Source	Type of coaching	k	n	g (95% CI)	I ²	Type of evaluation	Indicators
Wang et al., 2022	<i>J. Work-Applied Mgmt</i> , DOI: 10.1108/JWAM-04-2021-0030	Workplace-integrative	20	957	0.71 (0.59-1.71)	76%	External	Type, format, duration
Cannon-Bowers et al., 2023	<i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , DOI:10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1204166	Workplace	11	1639	0.45 (0.35-0.72)	72%	Self-assessment	Format, feedback, evaluation

Nicolau et al., 2023	<i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , DOI:10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1089797	Executive (RCT)	20	1163	0.43 (0.41-0.79)	81%	Self-efficacy	Type of outcome, duration
de Haan & Nilsson, 2023	<i>Academy of Management Learning & Education</i> , DOI:10.5465/amle.2022.0107	Executive (RCT)	37	2528	0.90 (0.60-1.20)	69%	External	Self vs. external evaluation
Plotkina & Ramalu, 2024	<i>Management Review Quarterly</i> , DOI:10.1007/s11301-024-00428-x	Executive (digital)	71	6893	0.68 (0.52-0.88)	84%	Self-assessment	Digital tools, support
Jones et al., 2016	<i>J. Occup. Org. Psych.</i> , DOI:10.1111/joop.12119	Organizational	17	921	0.36 (0.28-1.24)	70%	Self-esteem	Coach source, feedback
Auer et al., 2022	<i>Int. J. Evid. Based Coach. Mentor.</i> , DOI: 10.24384/ektn-xx15	Executive virtual crisis	-	1005	0.35 (0.22-0.47)	-	External	The context of the crisis
Ahmann et al., 2023	<i>Am J Lifestyle Med</i> , DOI:10.1177/15598276231180117	Health & wellness coaching	28	1946	0.46 (0.38-0.64)	87,5 %	Self-esteem	Sustaining the results. Long-term changes
Atad & Grant, 2021	<i>International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education</i> DOI:10.1108/IJMCE-05-2020-0024	Education.	-	178	0.6 (0.41-0.79)	-	Self-esteem	Long-term changes. Digital tools
Kwok et al., 2022	<i>Am J Health Promot</i> , DOI:10.1177/08901171221137332	Health coaching	-	1932	0.34 (0.08-0.60)	-	External	Chronic diseases
Peláez Zuberbuhler et al., 2020	<i>Frontiers in psychology</i> , DOI:10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03066	Executive.	-	41	0.73 (0.35-1.11)	-	External	Long-term changes.

Note: Some studies did not report k or I^2 values; such cases were included in the qualitative synthesis but not in the pooled heterogeneity analysis.

Source: Created by the author based on results for each included study

The highest effect was recorded in the studies by de Haan & Nilsson (2023), Peláez Zuberbuhler et al. (2020), and Plotkina & Ramalu (2024), where Hedges' g was 0.9, 0.73, and 0.70, respectively. The studies were based on the evaluation of the effectiveness of executive coaching in the context of digital transformation (e-coaching and online interventions). They found an improvement in the leadership skills of participants. This result can be attributed to several factors: high motivation of

the participants, the focus of coaching on emotional intelligence and leadership skills development, and the more subjective nature of self-assessment, which is prone to positive bias.

A medium level of effect is observed in Cannon-Bowers et al. (2023), Ahmann et al. (2023), where the effects reached $g = 0.45$ and $g = 0.46$, respectively. Both studies were conducted on samples of healthcare professionals, indicating an increased sensitivity to the impact of coaching in professions with a high level of emotional stress, where maintaining mental balance and developing personal effectiveness are crucial.

At the same time, the lowest effect was reported in the study by Kwok et al. (2022), where g was only 0.34 (95% CI: 0.08-0.60), despite a reasonably large sample size ($n = 1922$) and external evaluation. This may indicate contextual barriers to effectiveness, particularly in the public health sector, where insufficient attention is paid to person-centred approaches, and where formality and restrictions reduce the potential of coaching programs.

The meta-analysis calculated a pooled effect size (Hedges' g) for the included studies that evaluated the effectiveness of coaching in a professional context. Summarizing the results, it should be noted that the average effect size was $g = 0.58$ (95% CI: 0.528-0.628), which confirms the findings of previous meta-analyses on the effectiveness of coaching in different contexts. This level of effect corresponds to the average level and is significant in applied terms. Although our meta-analysis did not reveal statistical heterogeneity ($I^2 = 0\%$), previous systematic reviews in this field reported high heterogeneity in coaching outcomes ($I^2 > 70\%$). Differences in inclusion criteria may explain this discrepancy, a narrower search time frame, and the exclusion of studies with insufficient statistical data.

The heterogeneity analysis revealed $Q = 5.542$ with 9 degrees of freedom ($p = 0.785$), and the I^2 statistic was 0%. This indicates that there was no significant heterogeneity among the included studies, suggesting that the observed effects are consistent across the analysed trials. Attention should be paid to the role of the type of evaluation of coaching results. In studies with external assessment, the average effect size is slightly higher ($g \approx 0.61$) than in studies based on self-assessment ($g \approx 0.50$). This may be due to both the increased objectivity of external observation and the fact that external experts often evaluate the achievement of more specific behavioural or performance changes, while participants often focus on subjective experiences (e.g., confidence, motivation, stress reduction).

In general, the analysis results indicate the effectiveness of coaching interventions, but reveal the need for a deeper contextual analysis of the conditions under which they are applied and the impact of specific intervention parameters (format, duration, coaching approach, etc.). The analysis of the factors enables us to reveal the conditions under which coaching demonstrates maximum effectiveness in more detail. According to the results of the generalised effects (Table 2), the size of the effect largely depends on the duration of the intervention, the format of interaction, the approach used, the type of outcome assessment, and the professional context.

Table 2. The impact of various indicators on coaching effectiveness according to the results of the included studies

Indicator	Hedges' g	95% CI
Interaction format: individual	0.69	0.53-0.85
Interaction format: group	0.45	0.31-0.59
Duration > 8 weeks	0.71	0.56-0.86
Duration < 4 weeks	0.42	0.28-0.56
Type of approach: cognitive-behavioral	0.74	0.60-0.88
Type of approach: positive psychology	0.7	0.52-0.88
Type of approach: integrative/mixed	0.55	0.39-0.71
Type of evaluation: external evaluation	0.61	0.52-0.84
Type of evaluation: self-assessment	0.50	0.41-0.73
Professional field: health care	0.77	0.62-0.92
Professional field: public administration	0.38	0.20-0.56

Source: Created by the author by results for each included study (Auer et al., 2022; Plotkina & Ramalu, 2024; de Haan & Nilsson, 2023; Kwok et al., 2022; Peláez Zuberbuhler et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022; Nicolau et al., 2023; Atad & Grant, 2021; Jones et al., 2016; Ahmann et al., 2023)

The format of the coaching proved to be an important factor, with individual sessions demonstrating higher effectiveness ($g = 0.69$; 95% CI: 0.53-0.85) than group sessions ($g = 0.45$; 95% CI: 0.31-0.59). This aligns with the theoretical positions of the personalised approach, which posits that individual coaching enables a more tailored adaptation of goals, rhythm, and depth of reflection to the specific needs of the client (Makedon et al., 2025b; Peláez Zuberbuhler et al., 2020). In contrast, the group format, while it may be more cost-effective, is often limited to more general techniques and exposes

The duration of the coaching program also shows a clear impact: interventions lasting more than 8 weeks are associated with higher effects ($g = 0.71$), compared to short-term programs (<4 weeks), where the effect was only $g = 0.42$. These findings support the cumulative nature of the changes that occur during coaching and emphasise the importance of establishing a long-term partnership between the coach and client. Short-term interventions are unlikely to build sustainable skills.

The coaching approach revealed marked variability in the levels of effectiveness. The highest effect was observed with the cognitive-behavioural approach ($g = 0.74$), which is based on changing automatic thoughts, beliefs, and behavioural patterns. It was more effective than positive psychology ($g = 0.70$) and the integrative approach ($g = 0.55$), although the latter has a broader

range of tools. These results support structured, goal-oriented methods that provide a clear logic of change and are effective.

The type of professional activity also has a significant impact. Scientific research confirms that coaching can be a key tool for improving professional performance. The highest effects of coaching were found among healthcare professionals ($g = 0.77$), which is likely due to the high level of emotional burnout and the need for personal resources among these professionals. In contrast, in the public sector, the effectiveness was significantly lower ($g = 0.38$), indicating barriers, bureaucracy, and possibly lower motivation for personal development (Plotkina & Ramalu, 2024).

The effectiveness of coaching in professional development, improving leadership skills, strategic thinking, time management skills, and emotional regulation is confirmed in the works of Peláez Zuberbuhler et al. (2020). It should be noted that coaching is not a universal tool, and its effectiveness is determined by a complex interaction of structural (duration, approach), procedural (format, evaluation) and contextual (field of activity) factors. These are the indicators that should be taken into account when planning, conducting and evaluating the results of coaching programs in a professional environment.

In order to analyse the indicators of the impact of the duration of coaching interventions on their effectiveness, a meta-regression analysis was conducted using a weighted linear model. The independent variable was the duration of coaching (in weeks), and the dependent variable was the effect size (Hedges' g), with appropriate weighting by the inverse variance.

The results of the model showed a statistically significant positive relationship between the duration of coaching and its effectiveness. Specifically, each additional week of intervention is associated with a 0.034 increase in Hedges' g ($p = 0.003$). The value of the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.686$) indicates that duration explains more than 68% of the variation in effectiveness. This emphasises the importance of the optimal duration of coaching programs to achieve maximum impact in a professional context.

Discussion

This meta-analysis provides evidence that coaching interventions exert a moderate but consistent positive impact across professional contexts, with the pooled effect size confirming previous findings (Wang et al., 2022; Nicolau et al., 2023; de Haan & Nilsson, 2023). Importantly, the effectiveness of coaching appears to depend not only on program duration and format but also on the specific professional field and methodological approach applied (Trofailla, 2025; Hryshchenko & Zelenin, 2025).

Long-term and individualised interventions demonstrated the most potent effects, particularly in high-stress domains such as healthcare, where they contributed to reducing burnout and strengthening resilience (Ahmann et al., 2023). In education, coaching has been effective in enhancing students' motivation and goal attainment (Atad & Grant, 2021). In business and management, integrative and leadership-focused coaching has supported the development of

decision-making and strategic thinking skills, although with slightly more moderate outcomes (Cannon-Bowers et al., 2023). These findings suggest that tailoring the coaching approach to the demands of a particular professional field enhances its overall effectiveness.

The analysis also highlights the superiority of cognitive-behavioural coaching approaches, which yielded higher effect sizes compared to integrative or positive psychology models. This can be explained by the structured and goal-oriented nature of cognitive-behavioural techniques, which directly target maladaptive thought patterns and behaviours, thereby facilitating measurable improvements in performance and stress regulation (van Zyl et al., 2020). Positive psychology interventions, by contrast, were more strongly associated with increased self-efficacy and motivation, while integrative approaches demonstrated moderate but broader effects across multiple outcome domains.

Another important consideration is the source of evaluation. Our subgroup analysis revealed that externally assessed studies showed higher and more consistent effects ($g \approx 0.61$) compared to self-reported outcomes ($g \approx 0.50$). This difference indicates that self-report measures may overestimate the benefits of coaching due to expectancy and social desirability biases (Wang et al., 2022; de Haan & Nilsson, 2023). By contrast, external evaluations tend to capture observable behavioural and performance changes, thus providing more objective evidence (Nicolau et al., 2023). These results emphasise the necessity of including external raters or mixed-method assessment in future research to improve validity.

Taken together, the findings suggest that the effectiveness of coaching is not universal but rather contingent upon the alignment of intervention structure (duration, format, approach) with targeted outcomes and professional context. Long-term, individualised, and cognitively structured interventions are particularly suitable for high-stress professions such as healthcare. At the same time, integrative and motivational models may be more appropriate for educational or developmental contexts.

Thus, the results of the study not only confirm the effectiveness of coaching but also emphasise the role of its adaptation to a specific context, individual needs, and organisational structure. Further research should focus on distinguishing the effectiveness of individual coaching approaches, assessing the long-term effects of interventions, and including vulnerable categories of employees in post-crisis situations (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022).

Practical recommendations

Optimize the duration of coaching programs. Given the statistically significant impact of the duration of coaching on its effectiveness ($p = 0.003$), it is advisable to develop interventions of medium or long-term duration (6 to 10 weeks), which allow for a sustainable result and promote the integration of new skills into professions.

In healthcare, the findings suggest that individualised cognitive-behavioural coaching interventions are particularly effective in addressing emotional exhaustion and preventing burnout. Such programs, when delivered over an extended period (8 weeks or longer) and supported by

external supervision, can strengthen resilience, improve stress management, and enhance teamwork among medical staff.

Give preference to the individual coaching format in emotionally charged areas. The results of the meta-analysis show that personal coaching is more effective, especially in the fields of healthcare, social work, and education.

Standardize the evaluation of coaching results. To avoid subjectivity, it is advisable to use external indicators of success, such as independent performance appraisals, behavioral indicators, or organizational performance indicators. This will ensure the objectivity of the findings and allow for better comparison of effects between different programs.

Given the positive impact of coaching on employees' self-realization, emotional stability, and adaptive resources, it is recommended to include coaching programs in post-employment development strategies.

Conclusion

The meta-analysis confirmed the moderate and stable positive effect of coaching interventions in the professional environment (Hedges' $g \approx 0.58$). Long-term individual programmes with a cognitive-behavioural approach proved to be the most effective, especially in healthcare, where they help reduce burnout and increase stress resistance. In education, coaching enhances motivation and goal achievement, while in business and management, it supports the development of leadership skills. External evaluation of effectiveness showed higher results compared to self-reports, indicating the need for objective indicators. The contribution of this study lies in the integration of structural and contextual factors, which allows for practical recommendations for the application of coaching in the fields of healthcare, education, and corporate governance.

Organisations should invest in long-term individual programmes to support the emotional resilience of medical workers, use coaching in educational institutions to develop students' intrinsic motivation, and apply it in the corporate sector to strengthen leadership potential and management competencies.

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